

Chemistry of fluorinated 1,3-diketones and related compounds

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Manuscript received 4 April 2001

Notwithstanding the manifold uses of fluorinated 1,3-diketones and related compounds in diverse areas and their interdisciplinary significance, very few reviews have appeared on the subject. The present review briefly attempts to describe the work done during the last four decades.

The chemistry of fluorinated 1,3-diketones and related compounds has received considerable attention in recent years in view of their interdisciplinary significance and diverse uses. However, not many reviews have appeared on the subject except a comprehensive one in 1973 by Mushak *et al.*¹

Carbonyl compounds, having a second carbonyl group at β -position, are termed as β -diketones. According to IUPAC nomenclature, they are also known as 1,3-diketones. In 1,3-diketones, the two carbonyl groups are separated by a methylene or a substituted methylene group. Keto-enol tautomerism is the general characteristic of this subclass of organic compounds. A number of open-chain and cyclic structures, with/without hydrogen bonding, are possible as shown below (1-5).

The introduction of perfluoro groups in such systems imparts interesting and novel properties to these compounds. A few of them are indispensable reagents in analytical chemistry and the uses include analyzing lunar samples², cobalt in vitamin B₁₂³ and detection of other trace elements in blood, serum and other essential biological materials¹. A recent use includes supercritical fluid extraction of metals with fluorinated diketones as chelate forming agents⁴⁻⁷. Fluorinated diketones have been used as bactericides and fungicides⁸, in the solvent extraction of zinc⁹ and vanadium¹⁰ as also in the electroreduction of complexes of nickel¹¹. Recently, luminescence quenching of lanthanides in complexes with β -diketones containing different fluorinated radicals has been carried out¹². The fluorinated 1,3-diketones pos-

sess excellent complex forming properties and thenoyl trifluoroacetone (TTA), furoyl trifluoroacetone (FTA), thiothenoyl trifluoroacetone (STTA) and heptafluorobutanoylpivalyl methane (FOD) are some of the well known agents.

The classical work of Urbain¹³ and Werner¹⁴ has further aroused interest in this subject and fluorinated 1,3-diketones and metal 1,3-diketones have found applications in such diverse areas as spectral studies, gas, column and thin layer chromatography, NMR shift reagents and in polymer industry. This particular Review is limited to the chemistry of fluorinated 1,3-diketones and a detailed study of their metal chelates is not being included.

Structure of fluorinated 1,3-diketones

The simplest 1,3-diketone, acetylacetone, exists in keto-enol equilibrium; the methylene group of this compound is flanked by carbonyl groups on either side which induce the formation of enolic form which in turn stabilizes by hydrogen bonding.

The effects of fluorine substitution on enolization of 1,3-diketones have been studied by Park *et al.*¹⁵. They have reported that in non-fluorinated 1,3-diketones (e.g. acetylacetone), hydrogen bonding is possible only in *syn*

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form (6) and not in *anti* form (7). In contrast, hydrogen bonding is possible in both *syn* (6a) as well as in *anti* (7a) forms in fluorinated 1,3-diketones, e.g. trifluoro-acetylacetone.

This explains the very high enolic content of fluorinated 1,3-diketones. In fact, IR spectra of such fluorinated 1,3-diketones show no characteristic C=O absorption band (1725–1708 cm⁻¹) which is present in the spectrum of acetylacetone. In IR spectra, intramolecular as well as intermolecular hydrogen bonding are observed in the regions 2700–2500 and 3000–2900 cm⁻¹ respectively. In NMR spectra, the presence of =CH- resonance signal at δ 6.2–6.8 and enolic proton signal at δ 13–16 provides substantial support for the enolization of such compounds. The direction of enolization in fluorinated 1,3-diketones (8) containing a perfluoroalkyl group, is always towards perfluoroalkyl group (9). The maximum enol content observed in such cases is 200% as the compound contains two enolizable systems¹⁵.

Joshi *et al.*^{16,17} studied the effect of various substituents on the degree of enolization in a number of fluorinated 1,3-diketones. The enol content (%) of some typical polyfluorinated 1,3-diketones are as follows : 4-FC₆H₄.COCH₂.COCH₃ (97.00), 4-FC₆H₄.COCH₂COC₂H₅ (63.40), 4-FC₆H₄.COCH₂COC₆H₅ (93.96), 4-F,3-MeC₆H₃COCH₂.COCH₃ (86.56), 4-F,3-MeC₆H₃COCH₂COCF₃ (94.11), 2-Cl,4-FC₆H₃COCH₂COCH₃ (92.38), 2-Cl,4-FC₆H₃.COCH₂COCF₃ (92.53).

Synthesis of fluorinated 1,3-diketones

Synthetic routes for fluorinated 1,3-diketones are similar to those for non-fluorinated diketones with certain exceptions. Preparative methods for non-fluorinated 1,3-diketones have been reviewed by Hauser *et al.*¹⁸ and are not being discussed here in detail. One review¹ has appeared on fluoro-1,3-diketones and metal fluoro-1,3-diketonates.

Some important methods are described below.

Claisen condensation :

Fluorinated 1,3-diketones are usually prepared by the base promoted condensation of a fluorinated ester with a ketone containing at least one alpha hydrogen atom. Sodium amide¹⁹ and sodium hydride²⁰ have been employed as condensing agents with benzene or diethyl ether as the solvent used for such reactions,

Joshi *et al.*^{21–23} synthesized a number of new polyfluorinated 1,3-diketones (11) and characterized them on the basis of NMR studies.

Ar = 4-Fluorophenyl, 1,3-difluorophenyl, 1,4-difluorophenyl
R = CH₃, CF₃, C₂H₅, C₂F₅, C₃H₇

Reaction of a fluoroketone with an acid anhydride :

For acid-catalyzed acylation of a ketone, usually boron trifluoride²⁴ is employed as a catalyst with an acid anhydride as an acylating agent. The condensation of ketones with acid anhydride in presence of boron trifluoride may be illustrated as below,

Synthesis from a non-fluorinated 1,3-diketone with the aid of perchloryl fluoride :

It is a valuable procedure for introduction of fluorine into the γ-position of 1,3-diketone. It involves the action of perchloryl fluoride on the sodium 1,3-diketonates²⁵,

R = R' = alkyl, aryl; R'' = alkyl, H

Anselme's method :

In this method, the fluorinated ester is treated with ketone, in DMSO, in presence of sodium hydride in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen²⁶. This procedure was extended to synthesize fluorinated 1,3-diketones and Filler *et al.*²⁷ synthesized some polyfluorinated 1,3-diaryl-1,3-diketones (13),

Enamine method :

Filler *et al*²⁷ also synthesized pentafluorodibenzoylmethane by the reaction of pentafluorobenzoyl chloride on enamine derivative of morpholinoacetophenone. The general reaction scheme is given below,

Friedel-Crafts acylation of vinyl acetate :

Filler *et al*²⁸ obtained 4,4'-dihalodibenzoylmethane $\text{C}_6\text{F}_5\text{COCH}_2\text{COC}_6\text{F}_5$ (15) by treating an aroyl chloride with vinyl acetate in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. This method was also extended for the synthesis of bis (pentafluorobenzoyl)methane,

A modified synthetic method for preparing these compounds at a low temperature and with enhanced yields has been reported by Joshi and Joshi²⁹; the acylation reactions of fluorinated aryl methylketones with ethyl esters was done at 0° in absolute ether medium under stirring.

Miscellaneous methods :

Fluorinated diketones have also been synthesized by α -pentafluoropropionylation of ketones and aldehydes³⁰ using hexafluoropropene oxide as also from per fluoroalkyl-

iminophosphorus³¹. Regioselective α -fluorination of dicarbonyl compounds³² have also yielded the desired diketones in required yields. Nikolaev *et al*³³ also reported the synthesis of a number of fluorinated diazo-1,3-diketones. He *et al*³⁴ prepared fluorinated 1,3-diketones by reaction of enamines with fluorinated acyl chlorides. Chambers *et al*^{35,36} obtained diketones by direct fluorination of cyclic 1,3-diketones. Fluorinated 1,3-diketones were also synthesized using *N*-fluoroperfluoroalkyl sulfonimide for fluorination of 1,3-dicarbonyl derivatives³⁷. Use was made of XeF_2 for fluorination of 1,3-diketones to give the corresponding fluorinated 1,3-diketones^{38,39}. α -Fluorination of functionalized carbonyl compounds using *N*-fluorobis[trifluoromethyl]sulfonylimide also yielded fluorinated 1,3-diketone⁴⁰. Shukla *et al*⁴¹ did thermodynamic studies of proton-ligand dissociation of some fluorinated β -diketones in dioxane-water mixtures. Standard molar enthalpies of formation of nine fluorinated β -diketones were determined by rotating bomb calorimetry⁴². The important fluorinated 1,3-diketones prepared are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Important fluorinated 1,3-diketones

Comp	Ref
1-Fluoropentane-2,4-dione	108
1,1,1-Trifluoropentane-2,4-dione	109
1,1,1,5,5,5-Hexafluoropentane-2,4-dione	110
1,1,1,2,2,6,6,6-Octafluorohexane-3,5-dione	111
1,1,1,2,2,3,3,7,7,7-Decafluoroheptane-4,6-dione	112
1,1,1,2,2,3,3-Heptafluoro-5,5-dimethyloctane-4,6-dione	113
1,1,1-Trifluoro-3-methylpentane-2,4-dione	109
1,1,1-Trifluorohexane-2,4-dione	109
1,1,1-Trifluoro-3-methylhexane-2,4-dione	109
1,1,1-Trifluoro-6-methylheptane-2,4-dione	109
1,1,1-Trifluorodecane-2,4-dione	109
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione	114
1,1,1,2,2,3,3-Heptafluoroheptane-4,6-dione	114
1,1,1-Trifluoro-5-methylhexane-2,4-dione	114
1,1,1-Trifluoro-5,5-dimethylhexane-2,4-dione	114
1,1,1,2,2-Pentafluoro-6-methylheptane-3,5-dione	114
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(2-thienyl)butane-1,3-dione	114
1,1,1,2,2-Pentafluoro-6,6-dimethylheptane-3,5-dione	114
1,1,1,5,5,6,6,7,7,7-Decafluoroheptane-2,4-dione	114
1,1,1,2,2,3,3-Heptafluorooctane-4,6-dione	114
1,1,1,2,2,3,3-Heptafluoro-7-methyloctane-4,6-dione	114
1,1,1,2,2,6,6,7,7,8,8,8-Dodecafluorooctane-3,5-dione	114
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(<i>p</i> -biphenyl)butane-1,3-dione	109
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(2-pyrryl)butane-1,3-dione	115
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(2-furyl)butane-1,3-dione	109
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)butane-1,3-dione	116
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(2-methoxyphenyl)butane-1,3-dione	116

<i>Table-1(contd.)</i>	
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(2,5-dimethoxyphenyl)butane-1,3-dione	116
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(2-fluorenyl)butane-1,3-dione	116
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(3-phenanthryl)butane-1,3-dione	116
1-(4'-Fluorophenyl)-3-(3'-pyridyl)propane-1,3-dione	17
1-(4'-Fluorophenyl)-2'-methylphenyl)-3-(3'-pyridyl)-propane-1,3-dione	117
1-(3'-Fluoro-4'-methoxyphenyl)-3-phenylpropane-1,3-dione	17
1-(3'-Fluoro-4'-methoxyphenyl)butane-1,3-dione	17
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(3'-fluoro-4'-methoxyphenyl)butane-1,3-dione	17
1-(2',5'-Difluorophenyl)butane-1,3-dione	17
1-(2',4'-Difluorophenyl)butane-1,3-dione	17
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(2',5'-difluorophenyl)butane-1,3-dione	17
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(2',4'-difluorophenyl)pentane-1,3-dione	17
4,4,5,5,5-Pentafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)pentane-1,3-dione	17
1-(3'-Fluoro-4'-methoxyphenyl)pentane-1,3-dione	17
1-(3'-Fluoro-4'-methoxyphenyl)hexane-1,3-dione	17
4,4,5,5,5-Pentafluoro-1-(2',5-difluorophenyl)pentane-1,3-dione	17
4,4,5,5,5-Pentafluoro-1-(3'-fluoro-4'-methoxyphenyl)-pentane-1,3-dione	17
1-(4'-Fluorophenyl)butane-1,3-dione	16
1-(2'-Fluoro-5'-methylphenyl)butane-1,3-dione	16
1-(4'-Fluoro-3'-methylphenyl)butane-1,3-dione	16
1-(4'-Fluoro-2'-methylphenyl)butane-1,3-dione	16
1-(3'-Chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)butane-1,3-dione	16
1-(2'-Chloro-5'-fluorophenyl)butane-1,3-dione	16
1-(5'-Fluoro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)butane-1,3-dione	16
1-(2'-Chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)butane-1,3-dione	16
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(4'-fluoro-3'-methylphenyl)butane-1,3-dione	16
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(4'-fluoro-2'-methylphenyl)butane-1,3-dione	16
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(2'-fluoro-5'-methylphenyl)butane-1,3-dione	16
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(3'-chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)butane-1,3-dione	16
4,4,4-Trifluoro-1-(2'-chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)butane-1,3-dione	16
1-(4'-Fluorophenyl)pentane-1,3-dione	16
1-(2'-Fluoro-5'-methylphenyl)pentane-1,3-dione	16
1-(3'-Chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)pentane-1,3-dione	16
1-(2'-Chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)pentane-1,3-dione	16
1-(4'-Fluorophenyl)hexane-1,3-dione	16
1-(2'-Fluoro-5'-methylphenyl)hexane-1,3-dione	16
1-(3'-Chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)hexane-1,3-dione	16
1-(2'-Chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)hexane-1,3-dione	16
1-(4'-Fluorophenyl)heptane-1,3-dione	16
1-(2'-Fluoro-5'-methylphenyl)heptane-1,3-dione	16
1-(3'-Chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)heptane-1,3-dione	16
1-(2'-Chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)heptane-1,3-dione	16
1-(4'-Fluorophenyl)-3-phenylpropane-1,3-dione	16
1-(2'-Fluoro-5'-methylphenyl)-3-phenylpropane-1,3-dione	16
1-(3'-Chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)-3-phenylpropane-1,3-dione	16
1-(2'-Chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)-3-phenylpropane-1,3-dione	16

<i>Table-1(contd.)</i>	
1,3-Bis(4'-fluorophenyl)propane-1,3-dione	16
1-(2'-Fluoro-5'-methylphenyl)-3-(4'-fluorophenyl)-propane-1,3-dione	16
1-(3'-Chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)-3-(4'-fluorophenyl)-propane-1,3-dione	16
1-(2'-Chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)-3-(4'-fluorophenyl)-propane-1,3-dione	16
5,5,6,6-Tetrafluorohexane-2,4-dione	117
6,6,7,7-Tetrafluorohexane-2,4-dione	117
4,4,5,5-Tetrafluoro-1-(phenyl)pentane-3,5-dione	117
1,1-Difluoropentane-2,4-dione	118
1,1-Difluorohexane-2,4-dione	118
4,4-Difluoro-1-(phenyl)butane-1,3-dione	118
4-Chloro-1,1,1-trifluorobutane-2,4-dione	119
4-Bromo-1,1,1-trifluorobutane-2,4-dione	119
1-(Pentafluorophenyl)-4,4,5,5,5-pentafluoropentane-1,3-dione	120

Reactions of fluorinated 1,3-diketones

Acidity of methylene hydrogens :

The reactivity of 1,3-diketones is ascribed to the presence of a reactive methylene group and their occurrence in keto-enol forms. Substitutions of fluorine for hydrogen in 1,3-diketones results in a marked increase in the acidity of the methylene hydrogens.

1,3-Diketone	pK_a
Pentan-2,4-dione	8.9
1,1,1-Trifluoropentan-2,4-dione	6.7
1,1,1,5,5,5-Hexafluoropentan-2,4-dione	4.6

Further, the introduction of fluorine enhances the reactivity of the carbonyl functions in 1,3-diketones towards nucleophilic agents, particularly water and lower alcohols, e.g. hexafluoroacetylacetone reacts with water and methanol to yield the corresponding tetrol⁴³ and hemiketal⁴⁴, respectively. In the presence of strong acid systems, fluorinated 1,3-diketones undergo protonation. Using the acid system HF-SbF₃, the 1,3-diketones H(hfa), H(tfa), H(tta) rearrange to the allylic carbonium ion⁴⁵ (16).

Uses of 1,3-diketones as reaction intermediates for the synthesis of bioactive heterocycles :

Fluorinated 1,3-diketones have been used as reaction intermediates for synthesis of different types of bioactive heterocycles. Some of the more important reactions are being outlined below.

Reactions with hydrazine derivatives : Reactions of a

diazepines⁵⁹ (25) and 1,5-benzodiazepines⁶⁰ (26), respectively.

R, R' = CH₃, C₂H₅, C₆H₄ or substituted fluorophenyl.

A number of interesting compounds have been obtained when fluorinated 1,3-diketones are treated with amines⁶¹, polyamines⁶² and ethylenediamine^{63,64}.

Reaction with diazonium salts : Diazonium salts attack at active methylene group of 1,3-diketones to produce the corresponding diazo salts which can further be cyclized with different nucleophiles to generate different heterocycles, viz. (i) pyrazoles (27) with hydrazine hydrate⁶⁵, (ii) pyrazole-1-amides (28) with semicarbazide⁶⁵, (iii) *N*-phenylpyrazoles (29) with arylhydrazines⁶⁶ and (iv) isoxazoles (30) with hydroxylamine.

R, R' = CH₃, C₂H₅, C₆H₄, or substituted fluorophenyl (24)

Joshi and Dubey⁶⁷ synthesized a number of pyrazolo[5,1-*c*][1,2,4]triazines by condensing fluorinated 1,3-diketones with 3-diazo-4-phenylpyrazole. A number of diazo transfer reactions of fluorinated 1,3-diketones have also been studied⁶⁸.

Fluorinated 1,3-diketones

A passing reference is being made here to the chemistry of fluorinated 1,3-diketones. The chemistry of these compounds has aroused much interest in laser devices⁶⁹ as NMR shift reagents^{70,71} and in analytical chemistry⁷². Under appropriate conditions, the enolic proton of a 1,3-diketone can be replaced by different metals or their salts, forming a metal derivative which is a characteristic of 1,3-diketones. Several reviews have appeared on metal 1,3-diketone complexes⁷³⁻⁷⁵ and only two on fluorinated 1,3-diketones^{1,76}.

The addition of a concentrated metal salt solution to an aqueous methanolic or aqueous ethanolic solution of fluorinated 1,3-diketone usually results in precipitation of metal chelates (31).

In recent years, synthesis of a number of fluorinated 1,3-diketones of Ni⁷⁷, Ru^{78,79}, Pd^{80,81}, La⁸²⁻⁸⁵, Ce⁸⁶, Eu⁸⁷, Fe⁸⁸, Cu⁸⁹ and Cr⁹⁰ have been reported.

An interesting aspect of the chemistry of these compounds is that the metal chelates may behave as sensitive heterocycles having a cyclic π -orbital, formed by the overlapping of vacant *d*-orbital of the carbon metal atoms of the ligands⁹¹. These systems have been found to undergo typical electrophilic substitution reactions of the hydrogen atom linked to *sp*² hybridized carbon atom and the metal 1,3-diketones have been termed as quasi-aromatic. A typical such study by us is in the case of fluorinated 1,3-diketonechromium derivatives (32) where chloro-, bromo-, and nitro-substituents have been introduced at the central carbon atom of the chelate ring under carefully controlled conditions⁹⁰.

Ar = 4-F C₆H₄ or a dinitrate; X = Cl, Br or NO₂
R = Me, Et, Pr, CF₃ or Ph.

Fluorinated β -thioxoketones

β -Thioxo-ketones could exist in any of the forms 33-35.

There is considerable controversy about their tautomeric nature. Livingstone *et al.*⁹² and other workers favour the enethiol form (35) on the basis of spectral data. In contrast, Klose *et al.*⁹³ favour the enol structure (34) on the basis of NMR data. Belcher *et al.*⁹⁴ reported that certain compounds exist in the ene-thiol form (35), whereas others in the enol form (34).

Fluorinated β -thioxoketones have received considerable attention in analytical chemistry as superior chelating agents

for extraction and photometric determination of trace metals⁹⁵. The volatility of metal chelates increases with the degree of fluorination of the ligands⁹⁶. Once the oxygen atom of the metal 1,3-diketonate is replaced by sulfur, bonding between metal and sulfur increases and hence, the quasi-aromatic character of metal monothio-1,3-diketonate also increases^{97,98}. The first metal complexes of β -thioxoketones were prepared by Livingstone and coworkers and since then, these have been used as ligands with a large number of metals and metalloids^{92,99,100}. Livingstone *et al.*¹⁰¹ reported the synthesis of nickel chelates of fluorinated monothio- β -diketones with nitrogen heterocycles. Joshi *et al.*¹⁰² did extensive spectroscopic studies of fluorinated β -thioxoketones and their copper chelates. Yokoyama *et al.*¹⁰³ carried out electrophilic substitution reactions in cobalt complexes of β -thioxoketones. Joshi *et al.*¹⁰⁴ reported the synthesis of a number of monothio-1,3-chelators, Das¹⁰⁵ calculated the dipole moments of some new monothio- β -diketones.

NMR shift reagents

In 1969, Hinckley⁷⁰ discovered that the addition of bis-pyridine adduct of dipivalomethanatoeuropium $\text{Eu}(\text{dpm})_3 \cdot 2\text{Py}$, to a carbon tetrachloride solution of cholesterol causes important selective downfield shifts in NMR spectrum of steroid and for obvious reasons, the europium complex was named as 'Shift reagent'. The discovery at once suggested that it could lead to simplification of spectra by removal of signal coincidence and also characterization of nucleus in terms of its geometrical relationship with respect to one or more distant functional groups.

A novel and efficient NMR shift reagent, tetrakis(1,1)-trifluoro-4-phenylbutane-2,4-dionato)uranium $\text{U}(\text{btfa})_4$ has been prepared¹⁰⁶. It is capable of forming adducts with Lewis bases (e.g. Py and *n*-BuOH) and inducing proton shifts of a magnitude similar to those obtained with $\text{Eu}(\text{dpm})_3 \cdot \text{Eu}^{\text{III}}$ ¹⁰⁷ chelates of fluorinated 1,3-diketones, e.g. H(fod) and H(tfacaml) have been used as effective NMR shifts reagents.

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